

Parachor and Ring Structure. Part II. The Spatial Configuration of Bridged-ring Compounds.

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At first sight it would appear that bridged-rings, *e.g.*, camphor consist of two fused five membered rings having three common atoms. In the fusion of rings with two common atoms, there is no change in the form of either ring, which retains its individual property intact. This is the case with naphthalene, and generally with all the ring systems having two common atoms. The parachor of such ring system is the sum of the parachor of the individual rings, as shown in previous communications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 499, 671). Such is not the case, however, when there are three common atoms in two rings. In these cases the valency angle between the carbon atoms, and hence the amount of strain, must be altered to an appreciable extent and the nature of the rings, at least one, must also be changed. It is expected that parachor value of such ring systems will not be the sum of the parachor of the two separate rings. The object of the present investigation is to find out the parachor contribution of such ring systems and to deduce, if possible, the spatial configuration of such compounds from their parachor values.

In the present paper data are given for fifteen compounds. The surface tension has been determined by the method of maximum bubble pressure, as in the previous works. Two bubblers were employed for every determination and five readings were taken with each. The surface tension was calculated from the mean of these ten readings. The error in any individual determination is much below 1% (the error in the mean value is probably less than 0.5%) and as the fourth root of the surface tension is required in the calculation of the parachor, this error has practically no effect on the parachor value.

The liquids and the solids used were very carefully purified, the former by distillation, generally under reduced pressure and the latter by repeated crystallisations, until there is no change in the boiling point and melting point respectively of the substances.

The observed values of the parachor of these compounds are given in the fourth column of the following tables; the column headed

$\Sigma[P]$ gives the sum of the atomic and structural constants except that for the ring, so that the effect of this structure is obtained by subtracting $\Sigma[P]$ from $[P]_{\text{obs}}$ and is given in the last column.

Reduced Benzene Rings.

TABLE I.

	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	$[P]_{\text{obs.}}$	$[P]$.	Diff.
<i>cyclo</i> Hexane	33°	0.7676	23.94	242.1	234.0	8.1
<i>cyclo</i> Hexanone	31°	0.9385	33.59	251.4	243.0	8.4
3-Methyl <i>cyclo</i> hexanone	32°	0.9084	30.39	289.6	282.0	7.6
<i>cyclo</i> Hexanol	33.5°	0.9393	33.15	255.5	254.0	1.5
	98°	0.8804	25.96	256.4	254.0	2.4
<i>cyclo</i> Hexyl acetate	32°	0.9608	30.42	347.0	338.2	8.8
Menthol	98°	0.8399	22.54	404.7	410.0	-5.3
	150°	0.8114	18.38	398.1	410.0	-11.9
Menthol acetate	30°	0.9091	27.98	500.9	493.8	7.7
Dipentene	33.5°	0.8523	27.45	365.3	368.0	-2.7
	97°	0.8021	21.41	364.9	368.0	-3.1

It will be seen from the above table that the parachor contribution of the fully reduced benzene ring is about 8.1. The low value in the case of *cyclo*hexanol may be due to association. In this case the parachor increases with the increase of temperature indicating that the molecules are probably associated. This is further confirmed by studying the corresponding acetate derivative, where this association is prevented and normal parachor value is obtained. For the association between two molecules of a hydroxylic compound Sidgwick and Sutton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1461) observed a parachor decrease of 7.2 per molecule. Adding this to the observed parachor value of *cyclo*hexanol, 8.7 is obtained as the parachor contribution of the *cyclo*hexanol ring, which agrees quite satisfactorily with the mean value. It appears that menthol is also similarly associated. Abnormal result is also obtained in the case of dipentene but here the presence of a double bond in the ring complicates the matter.

It is of great interest to note that the parachor contribution of a *cyclo*hexane ring (8.2) is different from that of the benzene ring (6.1). This is in accord with the modern researches on *cyclo*hexane rings

(Sachse, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 1363; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1892, **10**, 203; 1893, **11**, 185; Mohr, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1918, **98**, 315; 1922, **103**, 316), which have definitely shown that a rigid planar structure of such compounds is no longer tenable. Such a bent structure will possess one or other of the following forms:

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

The present observed parachors demonstrate strikingly the difference between the benzene and cyclohexane rings and lends additional support to the Sachse structure (*loc. cit.*) from an entirely new standpoint.

Bridged-ring Compounds.

TABLE II.

	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	[P] _{obs.}	[P].	Diff.
Camphor oxime	130°	0·9526	25·35	402·8	394·4	8·4
	145°	0·9452	24·45	402·4	394·4	8·0
Bromocamphor	80°	1·295	31·93	423·8	415·7	8·1
	96°	1·276	30·19	424·2	415·7	8·5
Camphene	75°	0·8470	23·36	353·1	344·8	8·3
	95°	0·8242	20·97	353·1	344·8	8·3
Borneol acetate	32°	0·9764	29·74	468·8	459·6	9·2
	97°	0·9219	23·37	467·6	459·6	8·0
Fenchone	33°	0·9378	30·11	379·6	364·8	14·8
	98°	0·8867	23·39	377·0	464·8	12·2
	145°	0·8484	19·07	374·4	464·8	9·6
Camphor benzoate	94°	0·9969	28·78	594·8	582·5	12·3
	97°	1·001	29·09	594·6	582·5	12·1
α-Pinene	33°	0·8582	26·13	359·3	344·8	13·5
	97°	0·8050	19·97	357·2	344·8	12·9

It will be noticed from the above table that the parachor contribution of the camphor and similar rings is about 8.4, the only exception being with fenchone.

From the identical parachor contribution of the *cyclohexane* and the camphor rings, it seems probable that they possess identical configuration. It may be shown with the help of models, that a bridged (1:4) ring compound can only be formed from Fig. 1, without involving any strain (*cf.* Fig. 3).

In any other structure certain amount of strain will be involved. It may be expected that there is not much strain in the camphor ring for "nature tries to synthesise strainless compounds." "It will be seen that Fig. 1 is identical with Fig. 3 except that for the bridge. From the identical parachor contribution of the two ring systems, it appears that the camphor ring may be represented by Fig. 3, which has the additional advantage of involving practically no strain. In this connection it is to be assumed that the presence of the bridge in no way interferes with the parachor value of the ring.

Wightman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2541) has shown that Fig. 1 is sufficiently loose to allow of strain-free relative rotations of its carbon atoms and is stereochemically indistinguishable from a plane ring by reason of its mobility. It is expected that there should be no geometrical isomerism in Fig. 1 and hence in Fig. 3, which explains the non-existence of the geometrical isomers of camphor.

The cases of camphor benzoate and pinene become complicated due to the presence of a double bond in the ring, which prevents them from having a structure like *cyclohexane*. It is probable that in these cases only distortion of the electronic orbits takes place with a certain amount of change in the form of the rings.

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